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Development of Cu-Fe loaded activated porous carbon (CuFe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite) using sugarcane bagasse for photodegradation, antimicrobial activity and dye adsorption by batch kinetic studies

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Abstract

A novel hydrothermal method has been utilized to synthesize Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite that avoids any usage of surfactants. Wherein, Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanoparticle was synthesized in the temperature range between 120 to 180°C by hydrothermal method and results a greater reproducibility. The synthesized Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite and characterized by SEM, XRD, FTIR, TGA, Cyclic Voltammetry (CV), Electrostatic Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS), Electrostatic impedance spectroscopy (EIS) studies. Studies on the antibacterial activity and photocatalytic degradation of a chemically generated Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite were also carried out. The Kinetic model better fits the experimental findings of the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite. The kinetic adsorption results were studied using pseudo-first- and pseudo-second-order models. The second-order models primarily regulated the adsorption rate and exhibited a high correlation coefficient ($R^2 > 0.99$). Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite usually absorbs anions during the adsorption process of Methylene blue because, at acidic pH values, an increase in positively charged regions creates attractive electrostatic forces. The results of this investigation demonstrate that the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite effectively extracts the Methylene blue dye from the aqueous solution; hence, the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite exhibits a low rate of degradation during repeated use.

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Introduction

In the past few decades, activated carbons have found widespread use in energy storage and pollution control applications, including purification and separation processes (Choi, 2010; Huang *et al.*, 2014, Sarasidis *et al.*, 2017), toxic substance removal (Gokce and Aktas, 2014), gas storage (Sawant *et al.*, 2017), and supercapacitors wastewater treatment (Jin *et al.*, 2023; Xia *et al.*, 2023). High surface area and porosity, superior adsorption capacity, effective electrical qualities, eco-friendliness, cheap cost, and absence of secondary contamination are all necessary for these applications. The production of activated carbon to fulfill the demands of commercial applications has various advantages, as demonstrated by recent technological breakthroughs. The raw ingredients and the activation technique affect the properties of activated carbon (Boudrahem *et al.*, 2011). Improvements in surface chemistry with respect to functional groups and adsorption capacity, as well as pore structure and volume, surface areas, and improvements have been brought about by technological advancements (Lozano-Castello *et al.*, 2001). Researchers are working harder to find ways to produce Activated carbon from waste materials generated by agriculture and industry. Utilizing waste byproducts has benefits due to their accessibility and affordability. Numerous agricultural by-products with a high carbon and low ash content can be converted into Activated carbons. These include pineapple crown waste (Taer *et al.*, 2019), coconut shells (Mi *et al.*, 2012), rice husk (Mohanty *et al.*, 2006), coffee residue (Khenniche *et al.*, 2010), bamboo (Liu *et al.*, 2010), palm shell (Onundi *et al.*, 2010), and olive stones (Budinova *et al.*, 2006). In general, there are two established processes for making activated carbon: chemical activation and physical activation. Chemical activation combines the processes of carbonization and activation in one step. First, the raw material is impregnated with dehydrating chemicals like H_3PO_4 , $ZnCl_2$, K_2CO_3 , $NaOH$, or KOH . Next, it is carbonized at the appropriate temperature in an inert atmosphere (Mohammadi *et al.*, 2010). The process involves carbonizing the raw material and then placing it in an oxidizing gas atmosphere of

CO_2 (Sekirifa *et al.*, 2013), water steam (Zhou *et al.*, 2018), air, or some combination of these activating agents under a moderately high temperature (800–1100 °C) to improve the internal structure. As a result, carefully crafted activated carbon materials have demonstrated the ability to adsorb a wide spectrum of heavy metals and different kinds of electrode material. Lead, copper, zinc, chromium, cadmium, and mercury are examples of heavy metals that can have a negative impact on the environment and human health. At the moment, activated carbon is the most widely used adsorbent, and adsorption is thought to be one of the simplest and most efficient methods. Developing extremely specialized carbon types that are ideal for particular industry applications is one of the main challenges in the production of activated carbon. Activated carbon finds additional environmental use in energy storage applications, including the electrodes of supercapacitor devices, where it can be customized to fit different electrolytes with its large, pore-shaped surface area. The objective of this study is to create affordable activated carbon by employing sugarcane bagasse, a form of agricultural waste, and physical activation with CO_2 to prevent additional contaminants from chemicals used in the activation process. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray Diffraction, Cyclic Voltammetry (CV), Electrostatic Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS), Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), and Fluorescence Thermoelectric Reflectance (FTIR) were used to evaluate the Cu Fe_2O_4/AC nanoparticles. The main uses include photodegradation, antibacterial applications, and adsorption studies. Through the fitting and computation of kinetic models from adsorption investigations, the adsorption capacity of dye from an aqueous solution was examined, taking into account the effects of doses, pH, and temperature.

Materials and methods

All of the compounds were used without further purification because they were all AR grade. Sigma-Aldrich, an Indian company, supplied the following chemicals: copper chloride, ferric chloride, sodium hydroxide, Methylene blue, carbon black, nickel

foam, N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone, potassium hydroxide, and carbon black.

Fig. 1. Preparation of activated carbon

Synthesis of activated porous carbon from sugarcane bagasse

From a sugarcane selling location in Kadayam, sugarcane bagasse was gathered. The raw sugarcane bagasse was chopped into small pieces, cleaned multiple times in DI water, and then dried for 48 hours in the sun before spending 24 hours in a hot air oven at 80°C. Next, as indicated in Fig. 1, the dried sugarcane bagasse was finely ground with a mortar and pestle before being carbonized for four hours at 400° C in a muffle furnace.

Fig. 2. Synthesis of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite

Synthesis of copper ferrite/activated carbon nanocomposite (Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite)

Using a hydrothermal process, the copper ferrite (Cu Fe₂O₄)/activated carbon composite was created. First, 30 mL of deionized (DI) water was used to dissolve 0.023 g of copper chloride and 0.054 g of ferric chloride (1:2 molar ratio), which were then agitated for 30 minutes. After that, this mixture received 0.04 g of NaOH and was agitated for one hour. A 1-hour sonication was performed on 10 mL of DI water containing 0.05 g of Activated carbon. After that, for a full hour, both solutions were combined and swirled. After that, 25 mL of the mixture was placed in a 50

mL Teflon-lined stainless-steel autoclave and heated to 180°C for fifteen hours. After centrifuging the produced precipitate, ethanol and DI water were used several times to clean it. The precipitate as prepared was centrifuged and then repeatedly cleaned with DI water and ethanol. After washing, the sample was dried for a whole night at 100°C in an oven. As seen in Fig. 2, the dried sample was calcined at 60°C for three hours.

Photocatalytic activity

By observing the photocatalytic degradation of Methylene blue dye under UV irradiation, the photocatalytic performance of the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite was assessed. Typically, 100 mL of an aqueous solution of Methylene Blue dye with an initial concentration of 1 ppm was mixed with 0.1 g of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite. To attain adsorption/desorption equilibrium, the suspension containing the dye solution and Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite was agitated in the dark for thirty minutes prior to irradiation. Next, UV light was applied to the suspension. About 2 mL of the suspension was removed from the combination every 30 minutes during the irradiation process, and the photocatalyst particles were separated by centrifuging the suspension. A UV-vis spectrophotometer was then used to quantify the concentration of Methylene blue dye solution, which has a distinctive absorption at λ_{max} - 668 nm, in the supernatant. A spectrophotometer was used to measure the transparent liquid at 668 nm after the solutions were centrifuged. The degradation efficiency was calculated using the mentioned-below formula:

$$\text{Degradation efficiency (\%)} = (C_i - C_f / C_i) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where, C_i and C_f are the liquid-phase concentrations of dye at initial and final concentration (g/L)

Agar well diffusion assay

Using pathogenic bacteria such as Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* (a) and *Bacillus subtilis* (b), as well as Gram-negative *Escherichia coli* (c), *Enterobacter* (d), and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* (e), the antibacterial property of the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC

Nanocomposite was ascertained through the application of the well diffusion method. Various concentrations were employed to determine the antimicrobial activity of the aforementioned bacterial species: 25µl, 50µl, 75µl, and 100µl. Following a 24-hour incubation period at 37°C, the zone of inhibition of bacteria on each plate was assessed.

Sorption studies and kinetics

The following batch approach was used to determine the experimental data (Crini *et al.*, 2006; 2007; Gregorio, 2008) In each experiment, 100 mL of an aqueous dye solution at a known concentration at various dosages (0.1, 0.2, and 0.3 g/L), pH (5.5, 6.8, 7.8), and temperatures (30°C, 45°C and 60°C) was combined with 0.1g/L of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite. The flask was firmly covered. The adsorption of dyes on polymers is greatly enhanced by the presence of inorganic salt (Crini *et al.*, 2006; 2007; Gregorio, 2008). Either HCl or NaOH was used to bring the pH down to 8. At 30°C, the solution was agitated using a revolving shaker. A UV- Visible Spectrophotometer was then used to detect the dye concentration in solution at different time intervals by using spectrophotometry. Every experiment was carried out in triplicate with the same setup and was determined to be repeatable. To find out how the initial dye concentration in the solution affected the adsorption capacity, the dye concentration was changed. Additionally, investigations were carried out over a range of time intervals to ascertain the point at which the maximum amount of dye was adsorbed and the adsorption equilibrium was established. The mass balance equation provided by allowed for the calculation of the amount of dye adsorbed at equilibrium (q_e):

$$q_e = \frac{C_I - C_F}{m} \times v \quad (2)$$

Where C_I is the initial dye concentration in liquid phase (g/L); C_F is the liquid phase dye concentration at equilibrium (g/L); V is the volume of dye solution used (L); and m is the mass of sorbent used (g).

Results and discussion

Ultraviolet (UV) spectroscopy

To investigate the optical properties of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite, the UV-vis spectra were measured (Fig. 3). Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite have a characteristic surface plasmon resonance (SPR) band of Cu-Fe between 200 and 1100 nm, with a peak about 340 nm in the absorption spectra (Gregorio, 2008).

Fig. 3. Optical spectrum of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite

The carbon-coated iron and copper nanoparticles disperse efficiently in liquids and remain generally stable for up to three months, as seen by the solution's black colour.

X-ray diffraction (XRD)

Fig. 4 displays the X-ray diffraction pattern of the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite, which was produced via a chemical process. Diffraction peaks were discovered at 34°, 38°, and 64°, which corresponded to the crystallographic planes (111), (200), and (220), respectively. The Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite, which has a face-centered cubic structure, is represented by these diffraction peaks (JCPDS Card No. 04-0783) (Amit *et al.*, 2016). There are a few extra peaks since the material has crystalline flaws. These studies demonstrated the conversion of Cu-Fe ions to Cu-Fe nanoparticles by the NaOH. X-ray diffraction was used to quantify and confirm the nanoparticles' crystal size using Scherer's formula.

The estimated particle size was about 24 nm, in agreement with findings from scanning electron microscopy (Hang *et al.*, 2011).

Fig. 4. XRD spectrum of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite

Dynamic light scattering (DLS)

Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite was treated with ultrasonography and then suspended in ethanol. Using a particle size analyzer (PSA), the diameters of the agglomerated colloids in the suspensions were calculated. The measured particle size of 54 nm is in good agreement with the twice-larger crystallite size of Cu-Fe NPs (Ahn *et al.*, 2004). Fig. 5 displays the average and distribution of particle sizes for the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite. A coherent light source is aimed at a suspension of particles in DLS, and the light is scattered there.

Fig. 5. DLS image of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite

The scattering varies over time as a result of the particles' random Brownian motion and the ever-changing distances between the scatterers. When Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite is analyzed, the size of ionic liquid and activated carbon mediated nanocomposites as determined by DLS may look smaller than chemical mediated nanoparticles without ionic liquid. Activated carbon-mediated nanocomposites clump together quickly in the majority of investigations. In this study, DLS is seen four hours after aging. Previously, the size distribution profile of nanoparticles in suspension was established using DLS.

Fourier transforms infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy

Fig. 6 displays the results of an FTIR analysis used to describe the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite that was extracted from the plant. The wave number range for FTIR analysis is 450/cm to 4000/cm. Prominent bands of absorbance were seen at approximately 3432, 2923, 2853, 1633, 1445, 1024, and 584 cm⁻¹ in all three Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite solutions (Piyush *et al.*, 2018). As indicated in Table 1, the observed peaks correspond to N-H stretch¹, 2[^] amines, amides, C-H stretch alkanes, Nitrile C=N Stretch, C=C stretch (conjugated) alkenes, C-F stretch alkyl halides, C-N Amines, and C-Br stretch alkyl halides, respectively.

Fig. 6. FTIR spectrum of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite

These bands represent stretching vibrational bands that are responsible for the formation of molecules

like as terpenoids and flavonoids, and hence they might be attributed to the effective stabilizing and capping of the resulting Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite. The peaks showed that the Cu-Fe ions in the nanocomposites have several functional groups that were responsible for the stable Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite production (Crini *et al.*, 2006).

Table 1. Peak table of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC NCs

SL	Peak (cm ⁻¹)	Functional group
1	3432	N-H stretch 1°, 2° amines, amides
2	2923	C-H stretch alkanes
3	2853	Nitrile C≡N Stretch
4	1633	C=C stretch (conjugated) alkenes
5	1445	C-F stretch alkyl halides
6	1024	C-N Amines
7	584	C-Br stretch alkyl halides

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and EDAX

The SEM pictures of the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite are displayed in Fig. 7. SEM images provide evidence for the morphological behavior and structure of the bimetallic nanoparticles. Different types of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite were produced when NaOH was utilized as a capping and reducing agent. Cu-Fe NPs with approximately spherical agglomerated and indeterminate shapes were generated by the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite, respectively (Goldberg *et al.*, 2001). This may be because different capping agent types and quantities are present in different nanocomposites. This is further supported by the peaks' shifts and variations in regions discovered in the FTIR analysis.

Fig.7. SEM image of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite

To comprehend the semi-quantitative elemental composition of the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite, EDX analysis was performed (Fang *et al.*, 2010).

The peaks indicated the presence of iron and copper particles (Fig. 8). In order to support the purity of metallic nanoparticles, the total metal content was rather high.

Fig. 8. EDAX spectrum of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite

Fig.9. TGA analysis of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

Fig. 9 displays the TG analysis of the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite, which was created using *Desmostachya bipinnata*. The range of temperatures is 500–7000 degrees Celsius. The loss of nitrate compounds is correlated with the initial weight loss at 750°C. The breakdown of covalently bound organic material, namely nitrate, which was changed to oxide throughout the production process, is shown by the peak that was found after 2350°C. Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite DTA curves exhibit an exothermic peak between 100°C and 300°C as a result of nitrate component desorption and breakdown (Arun *et al.*, 2017). When the initial weight loss in TG analysis is less than 75°C, it means that water evaporation occurred on the sample's surface. Peak rise over this temperature is caused by adsorption as a result of organic material that is covalently bound breaking down. The predicted weight loss of the resulting Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite is 24.5%.

Fig. 10. Fluorescence spectrum of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite

Fluorescence spectroscopy (FL)

The fluorescence spectra of the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite at room temperature were recorded using a fluorescence spectrophotometer, as illustrated in Fig. 10. The measurements were conducted between 400 and 900 nm in wavelength. As seen in Fig. 10, the experiments' maximum wavelength emission intensities were gathered, and emission values were displayed as wavelength (nm) versus intensity (A.U). Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite has two distinct peaks, as seen in Fig. 10 (Ahmed *et al.*, 2016). The formation of the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite was ascribed to the lower emission peaks, measured at 413 nm, and the higher emission peak, detected at 725 nm. Surface imperfections were the cause of the higher emission peak, measured at 647 nm. In order to ascertain energy levels, fluorescence spectra were the preferred method. As the C Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite expanded in size, the fluorescence intensity rose.

Photocatalytic activities of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite for the degradation of methylene blue dye

As demonstrated in Fig. 11 a and b, the dye's degradation increased over time, peaking at 98 percent at 240 minutes. In the first five minutes, the degradation rose with an increase in UV light irradiation, reaching 5.6%. After examining the connection between deterioration and time, it's time to determine how it occurs. The mechanism was determined by examining the impact of time on the degrading process. Prior to being exposed to ultraviolet light, which excites valence electrons and permits them to move from the valence band to the

conduction band, the dye is first adsorbed on the surface of the catalyst (in this case, Cu-Fe-AC NCs). During this process, a positive hole (h⁺) is lifted inside the valence band (Prody *et al.*, 2019). Adsorbed water molecules on the surface of the photocatalyst will combine with the positive holes and free electrons to form ·OH radicals, while the free electrons will change the dissolved oxygen into superoxide anion O₂ ·⁻ radicals. These light-generated radicals break down the dye molecules into simpler molecules like CO₂ and H₂O.

Fig. 11 a. Percent degradation of Methylene blue dye with Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite

Fig. 11 b. UV-visible spectra of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite

Antibacterial activity

Examining the antibacterial activity of the generated Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite and its dependence on the selected microbiological species—namely, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas sp.*, *Bacillus*

subtilis, *Enterobacter*, and *Escherichia coli* was the aim of this investigation. Numerous bacterial species displayed zones of inhibition in the well diffusion method of antibacterial activity. The different patterns of the zone of inhibitions are shown in Fig. 12, Table 2. The Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite exhibited antibacterial efficacy against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative pathogens (Rivera-Utrilla *et al.*, 2001). After a 24-hour culture, pathogenic bacteria were cultivated in nutrient broth and swabbed uniformly onto different plates with muller hinton agar using sterile cotton swabs. On all plates, the purified Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite was added to each well at different weights, including 25 μ l, 50 μ l, 75 μ l, and 100 μ l. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours in an incubator. After incubation, the different zones of formation surrounding the well were measured (Abdelwahab and Shukrg, 2014).

Adsorption kinetics

The kinetics of adsorption was studied for its possible importance in the treatment of dye-containing industrial effluents. Numerous kinetic models have been proposed to elucidate the mechanism by which pollutants are adsorbed. To investigate the mechanism of the dye adsorption kinetic models were considered as follows. The kinetics of adsorption is important from the point of view that it controls the process efficiency. Various kinetic models have been used by various workers and different systems conform to different models but the Langergrens rate

equations (Ho and Mckay, 1998a; 1998b; 1999) for the sorption of a solute form liquid solution. In order to examine the controlling mechanism of adsorption processes such as mass transfer and chemical reaction, several kinetic models are used to test experimental data.

Fig. 12. Zone of inhibition of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite various bacterial strains

Effect of dye concentration

Fig. 13 shows the effect of dye concentration on the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite's ability to remove Methylene blue dye at starting concentrations of 20, 30, and 40 g/L when coupled with the nanocomposite. Since a particular mass of sorbent material may only adsorb a specific amount of dye, the initial dye concentration of an effluent is crucial (Benaïssa 2005; Bharathi and Ramesh, 2013).

Table 2. Zone of inhibition of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC nanocomposite against selected bacterial strains

Concentration	Zone of Inhibition (mm in diameter)				
	<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Enterobacter</i> sp.	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp.
25 μ l	1.7	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.7
50 μ l	1.9	2	2.2	2.3	2.0
75 μ l	2.5	2.5	2.7	2.5	2.6
100 μ l	2.8	2.7	2.9	2.8	2.9

By creating an adsorbent–adsorbate solution with a fixed adsorbent dose and varying the initial dye concentration for various time intervals, then shaking the mixture until equilibrium, one can test the effect of initial dye concentration (Salleh *et al.*, 2011; Bharathi and Ramesh, 2013). According to Salleh *et al.* (2011) and Bharathi and Ramesh

(2013), the instantaneous relationship between the dye concentration and the number of binding sites that are available on an adsorbent surface determines the effect of the initial dye concentration factor. As the initial dye concentration increases, the dye removal usually decreases. According to Low and Lee (1990), the

amount of dye that an adsorbent can absorb is fixed for a given mass of the adsorbent.

Fig. 13. Effect of specific dye uptake at different dye concentration with time (mints)

There will be vacant active sites on the adsorbent surface at low concentrations, and as the initial dye concentration rises, there won't be as many active sites available for the dye molecules to adsorb (Kannan and Sundaram 2001; Bharathi and Ramesh, 2013). According to Low and Lee (1990), as concentration grew, so did the amount of time needed to attain equilibrium. Yet, when dye concentration rose, so did the real amount of dye absorbed per unit mass of adsorbent. This might result from a high initial dye concentration and a strong driving force for mass transfer (Bulut and Aydin, 2006). However, Garg *et al.* (2004) found that at all dye concentrations under study, 100% of the dye was removed by granular activated carbon. Thus, the initial dye concentration has a significant impact on the adsorption. As the initial dye concentration rises, the adsorbent material's capacity is rapidly depleted. The fact that the total number of accessible adsorbent sites remains constant for all concentrations tested at a given adsorbent dose may be the cause of this. The amount of accessible adsorption sites decreases with concentration, hence the initial concentration determines the percentage of dye removed.

Effect of pH

Fig. 14 displays the proportion of dye adsorption at various pH values (5.5, 6.8, 7-8). By affecting the chemistry of the dye molecule and the adsorbents CuFe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite in aqueous solutions, the initial pH of the Methylene blue dye solution has a

significant impact, especially on the adsorption capacity. When Methylene Blue Dye is dissolved in water, its hue turns a solid red about pH 6.8. Methylene blue dye turns red at alkaline pH values (5.5, 6.8, 7-8) and dark blue at acidic pH values, but this red color is slightly different from original red at the neutral pH. At basic pH (sulfonate groups), methylene blue dye occurs as an anionic form; at acid pH, it exists as a cationic form. Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite was found to have a zero point charge of 6.8 (Rivera-Ultrilla *et al.*, 2001; Sumanjit *et al.*, 2013). According to Mall *et al.* (2006) and Sumanjit *et al.* (2013), adsorption of an anion is preferred at pH <, but adsorption of a cation is preferred when pH >. It was discovered that the values for the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite were 5.5 and 6.8, respectively. As shown in Fig. 14, the percentage of dye adsorption in the case of the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite decreased rapidly from 84 to 63% as the pH value of the dye solution increased from 2 to 12. The positively charged adsorbent surface and anionic dye exhibit a noticeably strong electrostatic attraction at pH 5.5. Both the quantity of negatively charged and positively charged sites rise and fall in proportion to the system's pH. Because of electrostatic repulsion, the adsorbent's negatively charged surface site is not favorable for the adsorption of dye anions. Additionally, excess ions competing with the dye anions for adsorption sites cause decreased Methylene blue dye adsorption at alkaline pH levels. However, because of a chemical interaction between the dye and the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite, respectively, there was still a large amount of anionic dye adsorption on the adsorbent above. The adsorption of Congo red on waste orange peel and activated carbon has been reported to yield similar results (Namasivayam *et al.*, 1996; Sumanjit *et al.*, 2013). (Namasivayam and Kavitha, 2002; Sumanjit *et al.*, 2013). This could be because there are a lot of positive charges on the sorbent surface, which prevent the negatively charged dye molecule from being rejected and increase adsorption. Generally speaking, uptakes in acidic solutions are substantially higher than those in neutral and alkaline environments. This hypothesis is consistent with the

pH effect data we have. It is evident that the aqueous solution's pH has a significant impact on the methylene blue dye's ability to adhere to the Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite.

Fig. 14. Effect of specific dye uptake at different pH with time (mints)

In the adsorption process, pH is crucial, particularly for dye adsorption. The amount of electrostatic charges that the ionized dye molecules transfer depends on the pH of the medium. Therefore, the pH of an aqueous medium will affect the rate of adsorption (Onal *et al.* 2006; Bharathi and Ramesh, 2013). Dilute 0.1 N HCl or 0.1 N NaOH can be added to the initial dye solution to change its pH. In general, the proportion of dye removal for cationic dye adsorption will decrease in low pH solutions, but the percentage of dye removal for anionic dyes will increase. On the other hand, the proportion of dye removal for cationic dye adsorption would rise in a high pH solution, whereas the percentage for anionic dye adsorption will fall (Salleh *et al.* 2011; Bharathi and Ramesh, 2013). Electrostatic repulsion between the positively charged dye and the adsorbent surface is lessened as surface charge density falls with increasing solution pH, potentially leading to an increase in the degree of adsorption (Wang *et al.*, 2006; Bharathi and Ramesh, 2013). The electrostatic repulsion between the positively charged cationic dyes and the adsorbent surface decreases as the pH of the solution rises, increasing the removal effectiveness (Ansari and Mosayebzadeh 2010; Bharathi and Ramesh, 2013). Changes in pH between 2 and 10 had no effect on the dye adsorption by coconut-based carbon, according to Garg *et al.* (2004). Maximum dye adsorption (96%) was seen in

sawdust treated with sulfuric acid at pH values between 6 and 10, with a reduction to 70% at pH 2.0. At a pH of 2.0, formaldehyde-treated sawdust removed the least amount of color (26.8%), and at a pH of 10, it climbed to 100%. To learn more about the adsorption mechanism, numerous researchers examined the isoelectric point (pIIEP) of adsorbents made from agricultural solid wastes. Because of the existence of functional groups like OH⁻ and COO⁻ groups, cationic dye adsorption is preferred at pH < pIIEP. At pH < pIIEP, where the surface becomes positively charged, anionic dye adsorption is favored (Radovic *et al.*, 1997; Bharathi and Ramesh, 2013). The adsorbent surface appears negatively charged in high pH solutions, as the positive charge at the solution interface diminishes (Ozcan *et al.*, 2007; Bharathi and Ramesh, 2013). Consequently, there is an increase in cationic dye adsorption and a decrease in anionic dye adsorption (Salleh *et al.*, 2011; Bharathi and Ramesh, 2013). According to Zawani *et al.* (2009), the optimal pH for Remazol black 5 adsorption on palm kernel shell activated carbon is 2, and the highest absorption occurs at 27.44 mg g⁻¹. After that, there is a significant drop in uptake. The carbon surface dye binding sites and the dye chemistry in water are both influenced by the pH of the solution. The carbon will have a net positive charge at lower pH levels. The electrostatic interactions between the positively charged adsorbent surface and the negatively charged functional groups on the reactive dye may be the cause of the higher uptakes observed at lower pH values. Additionally, the hydrogen ion serves as a bridging ligand to connect the dye molecule to the adsorbent wall.

Effect of temperatures

Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite sorption tests were reported at three different temperatures: 30°C, 45°C, and 60°C. Fig.15 indicates that the amount of color removed increases as temperature rises, suggesting that methylene blue dye is best removed from aqueous solutions at high temperatures. Raising the temperature causes the dye to become less soluble, which leads to an increase in adsorption. The dye ion's increased mobility with temperature could

possibly be the cause of increased adsorption. More and more molecules might have enough energy to engage with the surface's active site (Dogan and Alkan, 2003; Sumanjit *et al.*, 2013). Consequently, chemisorptions may be partially responsible for the rise in the sorptive absorption of methylene blue dye with temperature. An essential element of the adsorption process is temperature. Important information regarding the enthalpy and entropy changes during adsorption can be learned from a study of the temperature dependence of adsorption reactions (Dogan and Alkan, 2003; Bharathi and Ramesh, 2013). Temperature is an indicator for the adsorption nature whether it is an exothermic or endothermic process (Salleh *et al.* 2011; Bharathi and Ramesh, 2013). Adsorption is considered to be an endothermic process if its capacity rises with temperature. This could be because as the temperature rises, the mobility of the dye molecules increases and there are more active sites available for adsorption (Senthilkumaar *et al.*, 2006; Bharathi and Ramesh, 2013). According to Senthilkumaar *et al.* (2006), activation of the adsorbent surface and pore size enlargement are responsible for the increased adsorption capacity of activated carbon at higher temperatures. Certain structural alterations in the dyes and the adsorbent take place there during the adsorption process (Hema and Arivoli 2007; Bharathi and Ramesh, 2013). The system is made more random by the adsorbed water molecules, which are displaced by the adsorbate species, gaining more translational entropy than the adsorbate molecules lose. Due to a loss in adsorption capacity, rising temperatures may result in a decrease in the adsorptive forces between the dye species and the active sites on the adsorbent surface (Oladoja *et al.*, 2008; Bharathi and Ramesh, 2013).

Fig. 15 displays a plot showing the uptake of Methylene blue dye as a function of temperature (30, 45, and 60°C). It was discovered that dye adsorption was higher at higher temperatures than it was at lower ones. The curves show a clear tendency for the process to create monolayers (Namasivayam and Kavitha, 2002; Namasivayam *et al.*, 1998; 2001).

As a result, the chemical interaction between the functional groups on the adsorbent surface and the adsorbate should be the primary determinant of the adsorption capacity, which should rise as temperature does.

Fig. 15. Effect of specific dye uptake at different temperature with time (mints)

From a system design viewpoint, a lumped analysis of adsorption rates is thus sufficient to practical operation. A simple kinetic analysis of adsorption is the pseudo-first-order equation;

$$\frac{dq_t}{q_t} = K_1 (q_{eq} - q_t) \tag{3}$$

After definite integration by applying the initial conditions $q_t=0$ at $t=0$ and $q_t=q_t$ at $t=t$, equation (3) becomes;

$$\log (q_{eq} - q_t) = \log q_{eq} - \frac{K_1}{2.303} t \tag{4}$$

Where q_{eq} and q_t are amount of dye adsorbed at equilibrium and at time, in $mg\ g^{-1}$ respectively, and K_1 is the first order rate constant, was applied to the present studies of dye adsorption. As such the values of $\log (q_{eq}-q_t)$ vs t were calculated from the kinetic data of (Fig. 16-18) and plotted against time. The first-order rate constant calculated from the plots k_1 ($mg\ g^{-1}\ min^{-1}$) and q_{eq} ($mg\ g^{-1}\ min^{-1}$) values are shown in (Table 3). Adsorption kinetics for some system can also be described by a pseudo-second order reaction.

The pseudo-second-order equation based on adsorption equilibrium capacity may be expressed in the form;

$$\frac{dq_t}{q_t} = K_2 (q_{eq} - q_t)^2 \tag{5}$$

Where k_2 is the rate constant of pseudo-second-order adsorption. Integrating equation (4) and applying the initial conditions, we have

$$\frac{1}{(q_{eq} - q_t)} = \frac{1}{q_e} + K_2 t \tag{6}$$

or equivalently,

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{K_2 q_e^2} + \frac{1}{q_e} t \tag{7}$$

The equilibrium adsorption capacity (q_{eq}), and the second-order constants k_2 (g/mg min) can be determined experimentally from the slope and intercept of plot t/q_t versus t .

Fig. 16. Pseudo-first order plot for the adsorption of dye using Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite at various plot at Dye concentration

Fig. 17. Pseudo-first order plot for the adsorption of dye using Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite at various plot at pH

Fig. 18. Pseudo-first order plot for the adsorption of dye using Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite at various plot at pH

Table 3. Pseudo-first and Pseudo-Second order rate constant at different dye concentration, pH and temperature

Dye conc. (mg/L)	Pseudo-first order rate constant	Pseudo-Second order rate constant
20	$K_1 = 0.0264$; $q_{eq} = 1.049$ $R^2 = 0.9771$	$K_2 = 0.002$; $q_{eq} = 16.86$; $R^2 = 0.9929$
30	$K_1 = 0.026$; $q_{eq} = 1.264$; $R^2 = 0.9832$	$K_2 = 0.0009$; $q_{eq} = 25.12$; $R^2 = 0.9918$
60	$K_1 = 0.016582$; $q_{eq} = 1.1423$; $R^2 = 0.9625$	$K_2 = 0.0014$; $q_{eq} = 27.93$; $R^2 = 0.9781$
pH	Pseudo-first order rate constant	Pseudo-Second order rate constant
5.5	$K_1 = 0.0352$; $q_{eq} = 1.249$; $R^2 = 0.9473$	$K_2 = 0.001$; $q_{eq} = 16.50$; $R^2 = 0.9863$
6.8	$K_1 = 0.0246$; $q_{eq} = 1.148$; $R^2 = 0.9490$	$K_2 = 0.002$; $q_{eq} = 17.98$; $R^2 = 0.9937$
7.8	$K_1 = 0.0246$; $q_{eq} = 1.427$; $R^2 = 0.9082$	$K_2 = 0.001$; $q_{eq} = 18.38$; $R^2 = 0.9598$
Temp. (°C)	Pseudo-first order rate constant	Pseudo-Second order rate constant
30	$K_1 = 0.0301$; $q_{eq} = 1.159$; $R^2 = 0.9586$	$K_2 = 0.001$; $q_{eq} = 20.74$; $R^2 = 0.9687$
45	$K_1 = 0.029$; $q_{eq} = 1.1137$; $R^2 = 0.8180$	$K_2 = 0.002$; $q_{eq} = 26.88$; $R^2 = 0.9888$
60	$K_1 = 0.0184$; $q_{eq} = 1.064$; $R^2 = 0.9750$	$K_2 = 0.002$; $q_{eq} = 23.25$; $R^2 = 0.9793$

The applicability of the pseudo-second order models can be examined by linear plot t/q vs t respectively as shown in (Fig.19-21). The correlation coefficient R^2 shows that the pseudo-second order model an indications of a chemisorptions mechanism, fits the experimental data slightly better than the pseudo-first order model. Therefore the adsorption of methylene blue dye can be approximated more favorably by the pseudo-second order model. This model has been successfully applied to describe the kinetics of many adsorption systems. Calculated correlations are closer to unity for second-order kinetics model; therefore the adsorption kinetics could well be approximated more favourably by second-order kinetic model for dye adsorption. The k_2 (mg g⁻¹ min⁻¹) and q_{eq} (mg g⁻¹ min⁻¹) values as calculated are listed in (Table 3).

Conclusion

The goal of this study is to develop a one-pot eco-friendly chemical-based synthesis of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC

Nanocomposite. CuFe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite has been synthesized by hydrothermal method. The crystalline structure of the produced NPs was confirmed by XRD examination. The presence of activated carbon involved in the transfer of metallic ions to NPs was confirmed using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. SEM was used to assess morphologies and vibrational modes, DLS was used to determine surface charge and stability, and TGA was used to determine stability. Synthesized Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite has shown successful capacity for against bacterial strains. The synthesized Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite was also effective in the degradation of Methylene blue dye. Controlling the ratio of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite is very important to obtain good electrochemical performance. Kinetic studies were made for the adsorption of Methylene blue from aqueous solutions onto a Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite. This adsorbent exhibited high sorption capacities: the monolayer adsorption capacities were 20 mg/L (342.4mg/g); pH : 6.8 (28.4mg/g), 60°C (34.6 mg/g) of dye per gram of Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite respectively. The straight lines in plots of t/qt versus t showed good agreement of experimental data with the second-order kinetic model for different initial sorbent concentration, suggesting that the adsorption process might be chemisorption and physical sorption. The present research work established that Cu Fe₂O₄/AC Nanocomposite were excellent low-cost bioadsorbents for the removal of dye methylene blue. The kinetics data can be further explored for the design of an adsorber for industrial effluents treatment.

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